

THE ROLE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES AND MODERN METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Muhitdinova Nargiza Anvarovna

English teacher at the First Academic Lyceum of the Tashkent State
University of Economics

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Abstract: In this article, the role of advanced technologies and modern methods that can be used and applied in education today and help in the perfect learning of foreign languages, the achievements and opportunities achieved through information technologies and methods in the classroom are considered.

Key words: Innovation, foreign languages, modern methods and technologies, computers, "exercise system", scientific fields, methodologists.

INTRODUCTION

In the current computerized era, the role of foreign languages, that is, the role of English in human life, and yet the study of other foreign languages in the international education system is also developing. Various modern technologies and modern methods are being created for students to learn quickly and easily. Today, this language has become the main means of communication in society, and the desire and need to learn English is increasing rapidly. The application of advanced technologies, which are entering the world of science like a flood, opens doors to great opportunities and high achievements for today's young people learning foreign languages. Also, the introduction of new ideas and new methods is characterized by the increasing role of non-traditional learning technologies among young language learners.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As we all know, English is one of the most popular languages in the world today. The use of advanced innovative technologies in learning English is becoming one of today's hot topics. In the use of technologies and in scientific fields, the two terms "news" and "innovation" stand side by side, but these concepts are different from each other. "news" means a tool, method, technology, the word "innovation" is a process that develops in the educational system at certain stages. In learning foreign languages, the use of modern information technologies is one of the new approaches to the educational process, a new form of teaching and learning. One of the main goals of using contemporary technologies in learning and teaching foreign languages is to teach foreign language practical mastery and to form a communicative culture of language-learning students. It is fair to say that as we all know, the worldwide

spread of the COVID-19 virus has affected all the technological fields, including the education sector, and has increased the demand for modern technological tools, it would not be wrong to say that it increased even more. by the use of information technologies in science, we mean various computers, multimedia, videos and necessary electronic devices in the process of learning foreign languages. One of the things that attract the attention of students and young generations is technology, the Internet. Therefore, they can be attracted to teaching foreign languages through technology and various academic sites. These technologies are not only a technical tool, but also a new form and a new method of language teaching and learning. Because technologies that are developing day by day are discovering great conveniences for us. In current age of inventions, our youth can learn any foreign language without any problems.

It should also be noted that various modern methods are being discovered by methodologists of foreign languages in order to make the language teaching process even easier for young people.

The term "method" is translated from the Greek word "methodos" which means "way" and means research. Also, the concept of method is the activity of teachers and students in the educational process aimed at achieving the same goal and getting to know each other closely. Teaching methods are mainly practical knowledge activities for language learners. If we pay attention to the thought of Methodist scholars, methodology is a tool that helps to shape this thinking. Professor Boris Vasilyevich Belyayev, a major specialist in the psychology of language teaching, "comments on the formation of thinking in a foreign language"¹ is inappropriate, because the harmony of thought expressed in different languages is observed. if we pay attention to the thought of Methodist scholars, methodology is a tool that helps to shape this thinking. Professor Boris Vasilyevich Belyayev, a major specialist in the psychology of language teaching, "comments on the formation of thinking in a foreign language" is inappropriate, because the harmony of thought expressed in different languages is observed. if we pay attention to the thought of Methodist scholars, methodology is a tool that helps to shape this thinking. Professor Boris Vasilyevich Belyayev, a major specialist in the psychology of language teaching, "comments on the formation of thinking in a foreign language" is inappropriate, because the harmony of thought expressed in different languages is observed. In methodology, why? what? how? and whom? scientific considerations are made about teaching. The method of foreign language teaching means the set of activities of the teacher and student that ensure the achievement of the practical, general educational, educational

developmental goals of foreign language teaching. And if we consider that learning foreign languages is a process consisting of a system of exercises, it will not be a mistake. Because the main basis of every language learning process is oral and practical exercises. These exercises help students develop their language skills. The term "exercise system" is considered a method of language learning, and foreign language methodologists are continuously discussing this topic. In the scientific studies of foreign language methodologists in Uzbekistan in the 1970s and 1980s (J. Jalolov, T. Sattarov, A. Soynazarov, etc.), the system of foreign language exercises is described in Uzbek terms as "formative", "developing", "improving". defined the division into types of exercises.

¹Б.Беляев. Психология владения иностранным языком. Докт.дисс-М.,1960

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The goal of learning, generalizing and disseminating best practices in foreign language teaching is to achieve positive results. Professor M.V. Lyakhovitsky, who has achieved plentiful scientific results in the field of research methodology, expressed his opinion about the experimental test: "When the investigated methodical phenomenon is scientifically based in various forms and put to the experiment, the experimental test takes place. We can mention again that the methodology of learning foreign languages as a science has more than 200 years of history. As we all know, there are enough changes and developments in all fields over the years. Also, during this period, we can witness that different attitudes and views were expressed to the methodology of language teaching. One of these views belongs to Academician L.V. Shcherba. According to his opinion, although the methodology of teaching any subject is a science, it is not considered a theoretical science. It solves practical problems. In particular, the methodology of foreign language teaching does not rely only on the evidence of psychology, but is based on general and specific linguistic studies. If linguistics deals with the laws of the origin and movement of language phenomena, the methodology can be an answer to the question of what to do in order to use the necessary language phenomenon in practice based on these laws. Also, the methodology is a tool that helps to form the practical knowledge of students in the course of the lesson.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, because we live in the era of rapid development of information technologies, it is necessary to teach foreign languages at a perfect level in a way that is understandable and easy for everyone, using these opportunities wisely. Nowadays, one of the main urgent tasks of our pedagogical scientists is to

ensure that teaching methods and methods meet the requirements of the time and to create more modern and advanced technologies. The various socio-economic relations and cooperation carried out in our country with several foreign countries increase our youth's interest in the life and customs of foreign countries, mainly in the education system and language.

The use of innovative technologies and modern methods in foreign language learning shows that they help students to be active in the learning process and develop the ability to think logically, and awaken the passion for knowledge in passive students. Also these technologies help the teacher to work more individually with passive students. Including this sentence, the process of learning foreign languages is considered perfect, and in this process a person experiences complex psychological changes. Because there is a process of comparison between the mother tongue and the foreign language being studied. Using modern pedagogical technologies, teaching a foreign language with a comparison of the native language gives an effective result. Also, methodological skills and technologies play an important role in teaching foreign languages. In the process of correcting pronunciation and forming correct pronunciation in foreign languages, multimedia and electronic applications and other technologies play a major role. Exercises are the basis of learning all knowledge. The process of practical implementation of acquired theoretical knowledge is a tool that closely helps to further strengthen knowledge, build skills and competences. In order to effectively organize the foreign language teaching process, it is necessary to have knowledge of modern pedagogical information and communication technologies.

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